

off. The result of the present work is in good agreement with the theoretical prediction based on the formal proton-transfer model suggested by Huyskens and Zeegers Huyskens¹¹ and the experimental study on the dependence of the polarity of the hydrogen bond on the properties of the hydrogen donor¹²⁻¹⁴.

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Viscosity Molecular Weight Relationship for Solvent Polyoxyethyleneglycol Systems

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STUDIES have been reported on the intrinsic viscosity of some polyoxyethyleneglycol fractions by Mueh¹ at one temperature, but so far no systematic attempt has been made to investigate the viscometric behaviour of these fractions at different temperatures. The intrinsic viscosities of polyoxyethyleneglycol fractions (ranging in molecular weights from 400 to 1540) have, therefore, been

measured in benzene and water at 30°, 35° and 40°. Relationship between intrinsic viscosity and molecular weight has been discussed.

Experimental

Benzene used was of B.D.H. AR grade. Conductivity water was prepared by distilling thrice distilled water with alkaline potassium permanganate. The polyoxyethylene fractions were quite pure except for their tendency to absorb moisture which was removed by prolonged evacuation of the samples before use.

Ubbelohde type² capillary viscometer was used for viscosity measurements. The accuracy in time of flow was ± 0.1 sec. The densities were determined pycnometrically, accuracy being ± 5 parts in 10^5 . Kinetic energy correction was applied to the viscosity data and accuracy was found to be ± 7 parts in 10^4 .

Results

The values of intrinsic viscosity obtained from the extrapolation of the plots of η_{sp}/C vs. C and $\ln \eta_r/C$ vs C are given in Table 1. A survey of the data

Mol. Wt. (M)	Polymer-Benzene Systems [η] (ml/gm)		
	30°	35°	40°
400	2.40	2.38	1.96
1000	4.43	4.35	4.25
1500	5.34	4.90	4.28
1540	6.48	5.94	5.57
	Polymer-Water Systems		
	30°	35°	40°
400	3.37	1.66	0.70
1000	5.10	4.39	2.48
1500	6.58	6.11	2.64
1540	8.03	7.30	3.56

reveals the following facts :

(i) The intrinsic viscosity increases with an increase in molecular weight of the polymer and decreases with the rise in temperature in both the solvents.

(ii) Water may be considered a better solvent for polyoxyethyleneglycol than benzene at 30° and 35°. The results agree with the published data of Lakanpal et al³, on the heat of mixing of these polyglycol-solvent systems.

(iii) The rapid fall of intrinsic viscosity for the polymer-water systems at 40° indicates the disruption of solute-solvent interactions, thereby showing that water is better solvent than benzene even at 40°.

The values of A and B constants for a given polymer-solvent system at a given temperature (recorded in Table 2) have been obtained by using the

TABLE 2			
Polymer-Benzene Systems			
A	0.890	1.14	0.78
B × 10 ³	3.63	3.13	3.22
Polymer-Water Systems			
A	2.06	-0.40	-0.05
B × 10 ³	3.06	5.00	2.98

method of least squares, from the intercept and slope of the plots of $[\eta]$ vs M in the modified Staudinger equation⁴:

$$[\eta] = A + BM \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The results indicate that equation (1) holds good to a fairly good extent in the case of low molecular weight polyoxyethyleneglycol fractions as has been found by Moacanin⁵ during his study of polypropylene oxides (ranging in molecular weights from 120 to 2000).

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Flow Behaviour of Bentonite Suspensions in Presence of Electrolytes

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THE modification of flow behaviour and flocculation of clay suspensions upon electrolyte addition has many important technological applications.

The viscosity of a suspension is always higher than that of the pure medium and can more or less quantitatively expressed through a modification of the theoretically deduced Einstein formula

$$2.5\phi = \left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

whereas ϕ is the total volume of the dispersed particles divided by the volume of the sol, and η and η_0 are the coefficients of Newtonian Viscosity for the suspension and pure medium respectively.

Real systems, however, show considerable deviation from equation (1) due to the non-ideal conditions, e.g., non-spherical shape of suspended particles, particle-particle and particle-medium interactions. The particle-particle and particle-medium interactions are highly sensitive to electrolyte addition in clay suspensions, which is reflected in their flow behaviour.

Experimental

"Ecogel" bentonite suspensions were prepared and characterised following the procedures reported in our earlier works.^{1,2,3} 100 ml. portions of the suspension of desired clay content were thoroughly mixed with different quantities of N NaCl solution and left overnight. The necessary volume correction was made in computing the electrolyte content and clay content of the suspensions. The viscosity measurements were made using a thermostated Ostwald viscometer and the density measurements at the corresponding temperatures were made using a thermostated pycnometer. About 1 hour time was allowed for temperature equilibration. The viscosity of water and density at the required temperatures were obtained from standard tables. To safeguard against water evaporation and consequent concentration change of the suspensions, the suspension containers were kept in a water filled desiccator.

Results

The viscosity data for clay suspensions of different clay contents in the presence of varying amounts of sodium chloride at 35°, correct to second place of decimals is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VISCOSITIES OF CLAY SUSPENSIONS (CENTIPOISES) AT 35°C IN PRESENCE OF VARYING AMOUNTS OF ELECTROLYTE (SODIUM CHLORIDE)

Sl. No.	Electrolyte Concentration (N)	Percentage of Clay				
		0.1%	0.2%	0.3%	0.4%	0.5%
1	0.0	0.74	0.77	0.81	0.84	0.85
2	0.002	0.73	0.76	0.78	0.82	0.91
3	0.004	0.74	0.76	0.80	0.84	0.97
4	0.006	0.73	0.77	0.79	0.85	1.02
5	0.008	0.73	0.77	0.81	0.89	1.05
6	0.010	0.73	0.77	0.81	0.91	1.09